

ISTITUTO DI INGEGNERIA DEL MARE
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Summary

The Institute of Marine Engineering of the National Research Council (CNR-INM) carries out activities in the field of renewable energy from marine sources. In this context, the ULYSSES and ULYSSES 2030 projects mainly conduct studies on the exploitation of energy from tidal currents. One of the activities currently underway is to design and build a scale model of a vertical axis turbine for experimental studies on the production of energy from marine currents, with the aim of conducting studies both on the hydrodynamic performance and on the conversion and control system of the energy captured.

The document describes main technical requirements for the realization of the Power Take-Off system (PTO) of a model-scale tidal turbine and its sensors equipment, to be used for experimental research. The configuration of some examples of existing scale model turbines was studied, and then a layout of the ULYSSES turbine was proposed compared to those well-proven configurations.

The ULYSSES turbine will be a horizontal axis turbine with three fixed blades rotor connected directly to a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (direct-drive PMSG). The turbine houses instrumentation to measure rotor thrust and torque. Additionally, an incremental encoder is integrated to allow for servo-control of the PMSG as well as to provide position and rotational velocity measurements.

Sommario

L'Istituto di Ingegneria del Mare del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR-INM) svolge attività nel campo dell'energia rinnovabile da fonti marine. In questo ambito, i progetti ULYSSES ed il suo seguito ULYSSES 2030 conducono in prevalenza studi sullo sfruttamento dell'energia dalle correnti di marea. Una delle attività attualmente in corso consiste nel progettare e realizzare un modello in scala di una turbina ad asse verticale per studi sperimentali sulla produzione energia da correnti marine, con l'obiettivo di condurre studi sia sulle prestazioni idrodinamiche che sul sistema di conversione e controllo dell'energia catturata.

Il documento descrive i principali requisiti tecnici per la realizzazione del sistema di Power Take-Off (PTO) di una turbina di marea in scala modello e delle sue apparecchiature di sensori, da utilizzare per la ricerca sperimentale. È stata studiata la configurazione di alcuni esempi esistenti di turbine in scala modello, e poi è stato proposto un layout della turbina ULYSSES rispetto a quelle configurazioni ben collaudate.

La turbina ULYSSES sarà una turbina ad asse orizzontale con rotore a tre pale fisse che collegato direttamente ad un generatore sincro a magneti permanenti (Direct-drive PMSG). La turbina ospita la strumentazione per misurare la spinta e la coppia del rotore. Inoltre, un encoder incrementale è integrato per consentire il servocontrollo del PMSG e per fornire misurazioni della posizione e della velocità di rotazione.

Contents

List of Figures.....	6
List of Tables.....	6
Section 1. Introduction.....	7
Section 2. Power Take Off (PTO) technologies for tidal turbines.....	8
Section 3. Design requirements of the ULYSSES turbine.....	10
Section 4. Examples of existing scale model turbines.....	12
Section 5. Proposed layout of the ULYSSES turbine.....	16
Section 6. Sensors equipment.....	20
Section 7. Conclusions.....	24
Acknowledgments.....	25
References.....	25

List of Figures

Figure 1 – Main tidal turbine component arrangements.....	8
Figure 2 –PTO configuration of PMSG.....	9
Figure 3. The performance curves for two turbines (SIT & OPT)_ flow speed= 2.5 m /s.....	11
Figure 4 – TTT scheme, closed-loop PID control and programmable load.....	12
Figure 5 – TTT turbine’s PTO system - Test bench array.....	12
Figure 6 – TTT turbine - shaft encoder and torque meter sensor.....	13
Figure 7 – TTT turbine’s DAQ - Electronic hardware system.....	13
Figure 8 – Section view of the turbine model.....	14
Figure 9 – Torque and thrust transducers, the slipping with the shaft going through and the motor.....	14
Figure 10 – DAQ cabinet with the Compact-DAQ chassis on the left and power supplies on the right.....	15
Figure 11 – Drive cabinet and its main components.....	15
Figure 12 - 3D sketch of the ULYSSES Turbine arrangement.....	17
Figure 13 - System arrangement and PTO configuration of the Model Turbine.....	17
Figure 14 - Generator mode – Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) control.....	18
Figure 15 - Motor mode - Speed control.....	19
Figure 16 – Section view of the HATT turbine.....	20
Figure 17 – The three coordinate systems of the blade root and the torque and thrust transducer.....	21
Figure 18 – Section view of the Edinburgh turbine model.....	22

List of Tables

Table 1 – Turbine parameters.....	10
Table 2 – PMSG data sheet example: see model 145STK8M, with 650 RPM.....	16
Table 3 – Model turbines parameters.....	20
Table 4 – The specifications for the turbine measurement range.....	23

Section 1. Introduction

Despite decades of development efforts in the utilization of marine tidal currents, it still remains largely untapped sources respect to the others renewable energy sources like wind. That's because the marine energies are more expensive and difficult to exploit than the land-based options. That request an improvement knowledge about the complex loads due to the interactions between tidal turbines and water flow, including with waves, and the effect of these flows on loading and wake recovery.

So far, many numerical modeling tools have been used extensively for the prediction of loads induced by water flow on tidal turbine. Therefore, physical testing in laboratory conditions is an essential tool to provide validation data for numerical models and insight into the physical processes of these flow/turbine interactions to inform improvements to machine design.

The document describes main technical requirements for the realization of the components that simulate the conversion system from mechanical energy into electrical energy (Power Take-Off system, PTO), and the sizing of the electrical and electronic components of a model-scale tidal turbine, to be used for experimental research in our laboratories under the ULYSSES and ULYSSES 2030 Projects. The aim is to understand the dynamic loading of the tidal turbine, to inform developers and help achieve survivability and efficiencies in the marine energy sector.

The experimental tests will be carried out in the towing tank basins and tunnels of CNR-INM with a flow velocity in the range 2-3 m/s. In addition, the turbine hub is designed to accommodate various blade designs with diameters between 500 and 800 millimeters.

However, the mechanical, electrical and electronic components, in addition to being able to work in extreme transient conditions, will be sized for a nominal stationary condition at a speed of 2.5 m/s and a diameter of 700 mm, which estimated a rated power of around 1.5 kW.

Section 2. Power Take Off (PTO) technologies for tidal turbines

In order to explain and motivate the basic layout of interest, a brief review of the configurations used in full-scale tidal turbines is given first.

The main component arrangements for a full-scale tidal turbine are shown in Figure 1, including a turbine rotor and the conversion system from mechanical energy into electrical energy or PTO system, that incorporates a mechanical drive train, a generator and power electronic interface, and a transformer in order to send the electric power production to the main grid.

Figure 1 – Main tidal turbine component arrangements

The turbine rotor, which captures the kinetic power from tidal current and convert to the mechanical power, usually has three blades as a trade-off between hydrodynamic performance and manufacturing costs.

The challenge with the tidal current conversion systems is to convert a quite low and variable input, that is the tidal flow at typically 2-3 m/s with up to 15% fluctuations, into a much faster and stable output, in order to deliver 50-60 Hz alternative current suitable for connection to the network. Usually, convert the high-torque and low-speed mechanical power into high frequency electrical power is done by utilization of a standard speed induction generator (IG) with a gearbox. The gearbox is a simple solution to achieve an input source speed adapted to the output required speed. This configuration has some disadvantages, such as low efficiency, need of lubrication and frequent maintenance, resulting into lower reliability of the whole system.

An alternative way to convert mechanical power into the electrical power is to use a direct drive synchronous generator (DDSG), where the turbine directly drives the generator, hence the denomination 'direct drive'. In particular, Permanent Magnet Synchronous generators (PMSG) are of interest here. In this topology, a power electronic interface as a full-rated

frequency converter has been used between generator and main grid, hence, the generator rotational speed is well-regulated over a wide range, including very low speeds that are typical for slow turning marine rotors (

Figure 2). The best performance of a direct drive PMSG for a variable speed turbine is achieved with the PWM controlled IGBT existing in the structure of a back-to-back converter.

Figure 2 –PTO configuration of PMSG

Since, the generator operates at low speed to produce sufficient power, a high torque is required. To achieve this minimize winding losses value and enhance the efficiency, direct-drive generators with multi-poles and large diameter are preferably designed. Therefore, the medium-speed PMSG with a single-stage gearbox shown by a dotted line in

Figure 2, is considered as an appealing solution with a lower number of components as compared to a DFIG with a multiple-stage gearbox and higher speed than DDSG concept. The interesting possibility in this category, is using the same frame both for the generator and for the gearbox, that is all the active parts of the generator are mounted around the secondary transmission stage, so the generator and gearbox can use the same bearings, while gearbox lubrication oil can be used to cool the generator, that leads to having the lowest weight and compact size.

Section 3. Design requirements of the ULYSSES turbine

The goal is to have a model scale turbine with a PTO layout as much possible similar to those of existing commercial turbines in order to support the industry in understanding the challenges of tidal turbine performance assessment.

As mentioned above, the direct-drive PMSG with fixed blades represents an appealing solution for Tidal Turbine Converter Systems, while the best performance of PMSG of variable speed turbine concept is achieved with the PWM controlled IGBT. Therefore, this will be the chosen configuration for the ULYSSES model scale turbine. The direct-drive solution should be preferred but, due to size limitation and cost reduction needs, a PMSG with single stage gearbox could be considered as a second-choice solution. Table 1 shows model scale turbine size and operation parameters and approximate data to determine generator characteristics.

Symbol	dim	Value
Turbine dimensions		
Turbine diameter	m	0.70 - 0.75
Hub diameter	m	0.11 - 0.15
hydrodynamic characteristics		
Vflow nominal	m/s	2.50
Vflow max	m/s	≈ 3.50
TSR_opt	-	5.00
TSR_max	-	10.00
Cp_opt	-	0.45
Cq_opt	-	0.032
Generator data		
P Rated	kW	≈ 1.5
P_max	kW	≈ 3.7
Q_opt	Nm	≈ 40-50
Q_max	Nm	≈ 100-120
Omega_nom	rpm	≈ 350-450
Omega_max	rpm	≈ 1000

Table 1 – Turbine parameters

Turbine dimensions are chosen to realize the largest model turbine that can be tested in both towing tank and circulating water channel with limited blockage effects. This yields a major constraint on hub diameter, between 0.11 and 0.15 m, that could be a problem to fit the PTO components inside the nacelle. The nacelle length is not an issue as it can be adjusted to fit components.

In the table above, a nominal testing flow speed of 2.5 m/s is indicated, in order to ensure adequate Reynolds number values for blade flow. A maximum flow speed of 3.5 m/s has been also given as a reference. This flow speed range has to be verified and possibly reduced to be consistent with thrust and torque meter limitations.

It is worth to observe that the model turbine with PTO is not tested by mounting to a dynamometer. Then, thrust and torque meter and encoder will have to be installed inside the nacelle. Requirements given by this installation shall be also considered, but are not addressed here.

In order to complete the definition of the operational requirements of the model turbine, an estimate of thrust, torque, power, and rotational speed (RPM) over a full range of Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) conditions from zero to free-wheeling has been obtained. To this purpose, numerical simulations have been performed by the BIEM-VFC computational hydrodynamics model developed by CNR-INM and extensively validated against experimental data. Numerical results for model-scale turbine operation at uniform inflow speed of 2.5 m/s are presented in Figure 1. In particular, two alternative turbine geometries have been considered (respectively, SIT and OPT) to estimate the effect of different blade design on the quantities of interest.

Figure 3. The performance curves for two turbines (SIT & OPT) _ flow speed= 2.5 m /s

Section 4. Examples of existing scale model turbines

Case 1: TTT (Tidal Turbine Testing) 1.5 m diameter model turbine developed by Queen's University of Belfast.

In the TTT model scale turbine, due to the dimension limitation and cost reduction, a PMSG with a single stage gearbox has been used, which is connected to programmable load by diode rectifier. Figure 4 shows the original TTT turbine's PTO design with conventional closed-loop PID control, where a binary array of load resistors is placed on the DC-bus, and a linear regulator is used to regulated demand torque on the turbine at the DC output terminals, by command from the central Data Acquisition system (DAQ).

Figure 4 – TTT scheme, closed-loop PID control and programmable load

Figure 5 shows the setup arrangement of TTT turbine drive-train, Power Take-Off (PTO) system.

Figure 5 – TTT turbine's PTO system - Test bench array

An absolute rotary encoder and a torque meter are included in order to provide higher resolution of shaft speed and torque for the PID loop, and control the turbine rotor speed (Figure 6).

Figure 6 – TTT turbine - shaft encoder and torque meter sensor

Figure 7 shows DAQ arrangement which is based on a National Instruments Compact Rio (cRio) running LabVIEW and further custom-made interface electronics and cabling.

Figure 7 – TTT turbine's DAQ - Electronic hardware system

Case 2: highly instrumented tidal turbine model, developed by University of Edinburgh.

The model has a 1.2 m diameter, three bladed horizontal axis rotor and is bottom mounted. An overview of the design is given in Figure 8. On the left, a section view of the CAD model of the turbine, while right Figure 8 shows the turbine tests at IFREMER flume tank with LDV system measuring flow velocity in the turbine wake.

Figure 8 – Section view of the turbine model

The torque and thrust transducer and the root bending moments sensors are all rotating with the turbine shaft but their cabling needs to be eventually routed through the non-moving part of the nacelle. This is achieved using a through bore slipring whose arrangement is shown in Figure 9. The picture shows the nacelle stripped of its waterproofing sleeves with the torque and thrust transducer, the slipring with the shaft going through and the motor. The close-up picture shows the connection between the cable coming out of the shaft and the rotor of slip ring.

Figure 9 – Torque and thrust transducers, the slipring with the shaft going through and the motor

The data acquisition system is based on a National Instruments Compact-DAQ USB chassis (cDAQ-9174). A digital I/O module (NI 9401) is used to log the encoder signal generated by the motor. The strain gauge bridge amplifiers used with all sensors provide current signal (4 - 20 mA) rather than voltage as it is more resilient to electromagnetic interference. A current analogue input module (NI 9203) is therefore used to log these (Figure 10).

Figure 10 – DAQ cabinet with the Compact-DAQ chassis on the left and power supplies on the right

The motor is powered by three phase 400 VAC mains supply through a four quadrant drive which is capable of operating the motor as a break/generator and which can dump the generated electricity into a recovery resistor located next to the drive. In addition to a standard miniature circuit breaker (MCB), the drive supply circuit is also fitted with a 30 mA residual current device (RCD) to make the system trip in case of accidental current leakage which could arise from water ingress into the motor or its wiring. The electrical cabinet containing the motor drive and associated supply circuit is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 – Drive cabinet and its main components.

Section 5. Proposed layout of the ULYSSES turbine

Considering various types of existing PTO systems and new concepts at development stage, the design and selection of cost-effective architectures for tidal turbines is an exciting issue, with several multi-disciplinary implications. A simple, robust and efficient PTO configuration allows to reduce investment as well as operational costs, by enhancing device reliability and limiting maintenance requirements.

Therefore, the configuration chosen for the conversion system of the model scale turbine ULYSSES, is direct transmission so called Direct-Drive (gearless) with a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG). As the configuration is a direct drive turbine, it therefore requires a low-speed generator, or namely a multi-poles PMSG. The technical data sheet of an example of PMSG, which could be suitable for the required characteristics (table 1), is shown in table 2.

		145STK2M		145STK4M		145STK6M		145STK8M		
Rated speed		Rpm	650	1500	650	1500	650	1500	650	1500
Rated Power at Rated speed	Rated power (1)(2)	W	571	1752	1307	3389	1962	4904	2633	6462
	Input torque at rated speed(1)(2)	N.m	11.2	13.9	25.4	25.2	36	35.9	47.8	47
	Efficiency at rated power (1)(2)	%	75	81	76	86	81	87	81	88
	Current at rated power (1)	Amps	1.4	4.3	3.2	8	4.8	13	6.4	16
	Voltage at rated power (1)(2)(3)	V	244	250	243	260	246	231	249	248
Rated Power at Half speed	Rated Power at half speed (1)(2)	W	204	690	493	1566	739	2319	1075	3097
	Input torque at half speed (1)(2)	N.m	8.9	11.5	20.7	25.4	28.8	36	43.5	47.8
	Efficiency at half speed (1)(2)	%	68	77	70	78	76	82	73	83
	Number of poles (number of pairs of poles)		12 (6)							
	Cogging torque	N.m	0.2		0.4		0.6		0.8	
	Phase resistance at 20°C	Ohm	19.8	4.53	8.6	1.4	4.11	0.59	3.18	0.51
	Phase inductance (5)	mH	105	24	60	10	34	4.9	25.8	4.1
	Voltage at no load (back emf) at 20°C (4)	V	365	393	390	367	357	312	361	334
	Rotor inertia	10 ⁻³ Kg.m ²	1.28		2.24		3.19		4.14	
	Weight	Kg	6.2		10.4		14.5		18.7	
	Power cable square section (6)	mm ²	4x1.5		4x1.5		4x1.5		4x1.5	
	Power cable diameter	mm	Ø8.6		Ø8.6		Ø8.6		Ø8.6	

Table 2 – PMSG data sheet example: see model 145STK8M, with 650 RPM

Figure 12 shows the 3D sketch of the three-blade horizontal-axis tidal turbine layout, while the general turbine configuration diagram was shown in Figure 13. DAQ (data acquisition system) has the role of acquiring and recording data from all sensors and also the possibility of sending the control command signal in order to develop the control system. The processor of DAQ can be National Instruments based (CompactDAQ or CompactRIO) consisting of a digital I / O module (for example NI USB-6211 16 AI) used to record the encoder signal and any other necessary NI gadgets. Another possibility can be the use of LabJack T7-Pro with analog inputs from 16 bit to 24 bit, and compatible with Labview, Matlab, Python, C / C ++, etc. DAQ will be enclosed in a metal cabinet complete with a power supply unit necessary for operation.

Figure 12 - 3D sketch of the ULYSSES Turbine arrangement

Figure 13 - System arrangement and PTO configuration of the Model Turbine

The turbine converter consists of PWM controlled IGBT for the generator-side converter, a DC-bus capacitor is placed to keep small the voltage ripple in the DC-link, and grid-side converter

which is considered a diode bridge rectifier. Furthermore, a resistance bank placed on the DC-bus output in order to dissipate the produced energy.

This configuration of the converter, in addition to giving the possibility to obtain the best performances of the PMSG due to that the IGBT converter is an active converter (capable of bidirectional power flow), also gives the possibility to operate the generator as a motor. The operating diagrams are shown below in: (i) generator mode (Figure 14), (ii) engine mode (here also called dynamometer, by analogy with the experimental equipment commonly used in the Institute for the experimental characterization of the models of rotors (Figure 15).

In order to control the PMSG, it was considering the Maximum Torque per Ampere control strategy by taking advantage of the Field Oriented Control (FOC) method. Using a two phase machine model (expressed in the rotor-oriented dq-reference frame), the number of equations is reduced and the control design is simplified. In the Maximum Torque per Ampere control strategy, if the machine has no saliency, then the torque is determined solely by the q -axis current. Therefore, by regulating the d -axis current (which makes no contribution to the electromagnetic torque) to zero, the maximum torque to current ratio is achieved.

For the **generator** operating mode (Figure 14), the desired (reference) q -axis stator current (i_{sq}) is calculated from a quadratic equation (eq. 1) based on the output q -axis voltage (v_{sq}) with an optimal proportional factor (k_{sq}), which is entered by the user.

$$i_{sq} = k_{sq} \cdot v_{sq}^2 \tag{1}$$

Figure 14 - **Generator** mode – Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) control

While, for the **motor** operating mode (Figure 15), the desired speed (Ω^* or rpm), which lead to the desired (reference) torque / q -axis stator current (i_{sq}), is set by the user (for example via the Labview program).

Section 6. Sensors equipment

In the following have been brought some details about the Torque and Thrust transducers of three model-scale turbine cases developed in other Institutes for experimental research:

- Scale model Horizontal Axis Tidal Turbine (HATT) of Cardiff University
- Marine current turbine model scale of IFREMER
- Tidal turbine model of the University of Edinburgh

In the table 3 some specifications of these three turbines have been summarized:

<i>Turbine</i>	<i>Generator</i>	<i>Gearbox</i>	<i>D-Rotor (mm)</i>	<i>D-Nacelle (mm)</i>	<i>V_{rated} (m/s)</i>
Cardiff	<i>PMSM</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>900</i>	<i>130</i>	<i>1.3</i>
IFREMER	<i>PMSM</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>724</i>	<i>115</i>	<i>1.2</i>
Edinburgh	<i>PMSM</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>1200</i>	<i>120 & 160</i>	<i>1.4</i>

Table 3 – Model turbines parameters

Scale model Horizontal Axis Tidal Turbine (HATT) of Cardiff University:

The turbine has a diameter of 900 mm and was designed as a direct drive HATT. The nacelle has a 130 mm diameter. Mechanical power conversion is obtained by a PMSM generator.

As shown in figure 16, it was created via two drive interfacing shafts to allow for the flanging arrangement to the thrust/torque transducer. Using two drive shafts also facilitated the positioning of the PMSM on back side of the turbine away from the rotor instrumentation. The structure allows for modularity in the instrumentation set-up and ease of part replacement. The design decision to position the PMSM at the back end of the HATT was also undertaken to reduce electrical noise in transducers signals.

The drive shaft was supported by three bearing housings; the mid support, front and back plates. The first shaft has a hollowed section to accommodate instrumentation cabling, which was fed from the rotating portion of the 18-way slip ring. The front shaft was supported by double row bearings, which act as the main thrust bearing and are housed in the front plate. A dynamic seal was embedded in the front plate to protect from water entry.

Figure 16 – Section view of the HATT turbine

The main drive shaft was supported in two places, at the mid support and back plate. The front and back drive shafts are coupled together to transfer torsional loads and rotational motion. The main shaft has been fitted with an encoder and slip ring to the left of the mid plate and a PMSM to the right of the mid plate with respect to figure 16.

A bespoke rotor torque and thrust transducer was created by Applied Measurements Ltd. The transducer used was an adapted DBBSS/TSF Torque and Axial Force Sensor, which had a rated maximum thrust load of 1.8 kN and a maximum rated torsional loading of 100 Nm. The transducer was adapted for the specified load rating, for waterproofing, to house two 18 way Lemo EGG.2B.318 connectors and to accommodate through wiring for hub instrumentation. The transducer was fastened between the front drive shaft and the turbine rotor upstream of any bearings or seals to measure rotor loads prior to any drive shaft losses. The transducer used two ICA4H amplifiers, one for thrust loading with a sensitivity of 0.005 mA/N and one for torque loading with a sensitivity of 0.08 mA/N, both amplifiers were housed in the body of the transducer.

Marine current turbine model scale of IFREMER:

The turbine has a diameter of 724 mm and was designed as a direct drive HATT. The nacelle has a 115 mm diameter. Mechanical power conversion is obtained by a PMSM generator.

Figure 17 – The three coordinate systems of the blade root and the torque and thrust transducer

Each blade root is equipped with a specific load-cell including 5 different channels: 2 forces and 3 moments. In addition to this multi-components blade root load-cell, the torque and the thrust applied on the main rotation axis are measured by the torque and thrust transducer. This waterproof transducer is positioned upstream of the seals of the machine to prevent measuring the friction effects (figure 17). The blade root load-cell and the torque and thrust

transducer are custom made by the French company Sixaxes (Sixaxes 2017) in partnership with Ifremer. The 48 shielded cables coming from these transducers are routed through a 52 channels slip ring enabling the rotation. These low voltage signals are amplified by an electronic signal processing unit, located outside of the turbine and of the water as well. The motor shaft is connected to the turbine shaft through a motor-gearbox enabling suitable torque and rotation speed ratings.

Tidal turbine model of the University of Edinburgh:

The turbine has a diameter of 1200 mm and was designed as a direct drive HATT. The nacelle has a 120 mm diameter from hub up to tower and 160 mm diameter beyond tower. Mechanical power conversion is obtained by a PMSM generator.

Figure 18 – Section view of the Edinburgh turbine model

The torque and thrust transducer was custom made by the company Applied Measurements Ltd (www.appmeas.co.uk). Sensors are located ‘upstream’ of shaft seal, and therefore in contact with the surrounding water, and are designed to be waterproof and made in stainless steel. The specifications for measurement range were based on the maximum rotor loads predicted by a numerical BEM model, with a safety factor of 2 applied. They are summarised in table 4. From calibration, the ‘interactions’ of thrust loads on torque readings and of torque loads on thrust readings are respectively within 0.06% and 0.11% of the load ratings.

Maximum continuous torque (Nm)	26
Peak torque (Nm)	100
Maximum measurable torque (Nm)	100
Torque transducer proof rating (Nm)	150
Maximum measurable thrust (N)	1300
Thrust transducer proof rating (N)	1950
Maximum measurable streamwise blade root bending moment (Nm)	62
Root bending moment proof rating (Nm)	93
Maximum rotational speed (rpm)	250

Table 4 – The specifications for the turbine measurement range

One of the key bespoke features of this sensor for this application is the cable routing. In addition to the six cables required to supply power and to output torque and thrust signals, 15 more are routed through the body of the transducer to supply power to instruments in the turbine nose and return measured signals. The transducer is fitted with a 19-way connector (model DBPU 104 Z092-139 made by Fischer) on the face bolted to the shaft and with a 16-way connector (model DBEU 104 A086-130 made by Fischer) on the face attached to the hub. O-rings are fitted at the interfaces between the transducer and the hub and between the transducer and the shaft. This approach makes it possible to conveniently route cables from the waterproof enclosure in the nose cone to the hollow section of the shaft through a waterproof environment.

Section 7. Conclusions

The document describes main technical requirements for the realization of the Power Take-Off system (PTO) of a model-scale tidal turbine and its sensors equipment, to be used for experimental research.

The goal is to have a model scale turbine with a PTO layout as much possible similar to those of existing commercial turbines in order to support the industry in understanding the challenges of tidal turbine performance assessment. Therefore, a brief review of the configurations used in full-size tide turbines was made.

In addition, the configuration of some examples of existing scale model turbines was studied, and then a layout of the ULYSSES turbine was proposed compared to those well-proven configurations.

The ULYSSES turbine will be a horizontal axis turbine with three fixed blades rotor connected directly to a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (direct-drive PMSG). The turbine houses instrumentation to measure rotor thrust and torque. Additionally, an incremental encoder is integrated to allow for servo-control of the PMSG as well as to provide position and rotational velocity measurements.

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References

1. Rafiei M, Salvatore F, Capponi FG. Generator Topologies for Horizontal Axis Tidal Turbine. *ELECTRIMACS 2019: Selected Papers-Volume 1*. 2020 Apr 25;615:447.
2. Frost C, Benson I, Jeffcoate P, Elsässer B, Whittaker T. The Effect of Control Strategy on Tidal Stream Turbine Performance in Laboratory and Field Experiments. *Energies*. 2018 Jun;11(6):1533.
3. Allmark M, Ellis R, Porter K, O'Doherty T, Johnstone C. The development and testing of a lab-scale tidal stream turbine for the study of dynamic device loading. In *Proceedings of the 4th Asian Wave and Tidal Energy Conference, Scottish, UK 2018 Sep* (pp. 9-13).
4. Allmark M, Ellis R, Lloyd C, Ordonez-Sanchez S, Johannesen K, Byrne C, Johnstone C, O'Doherty T, Mason-Jones A. The development, design and characterisation of a scale model Horizontal Axis Tidal Turbine for dynamic load quantification. *Renewable Energy*. 2020 Aug 1;156:913-30.
5. Gaurier B, Germain G, Pinon G. How to correctly measure turbulent upstream flow for marine current turbine performances evaluation?. In *Advances in Renewable Energies Offshore: Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Renewable Energies Offshore (RENEW 2018), October 8-10, 2018, Lisbon, Portugal 2018 Oct 3* (p. 23). CRC Press.
6. Gaurier B, Germain G, Facq JV, Johnstone CM, Grant AD, Day AH, Nixon E, Di Felice F, Costanzo M. Tidal energy "Round Robin" tests comparisons between towing tank and circulating tank results. *International Journal of Marine Energy*. 2015 Dec 1;12:87-109.
7. Payne GS, Stallard T, Martinez R. Design and manufacture of a bed supported tidal turbine model for blade and shaft load measurement in turbulent flow and waves. *Renewable Energy*. 2017 Jul 1;107:312-26.